

The Role of Time Reversal and Possible Number of Reactions on Equilibrium

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It is well known that one may derive the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions from a reaction balance equation linked with a conservation of energy statement for two body elastic collisions. In a reaction balance equation, one has two particles on one side of the equation and two on the other, so particle number is automatically conserved regardless of the math expression on each side. The question becomes: What does a reaction balance equation represent statistically? We argue that it shows that the number of possible reactions is balanced on both sides of the equation which must be the case due to time reversal, we argue. Thus, there is more than a consideration of conservation of energy and particle number, but also a conservation of the number of possible collisions. We then try to argue that this third conserved quantity is linked to a conserved function $F(p(e_i))$ such that $F(p(e_i) + dp(e_i)) = F(p(e_i) + \sum_i dp(e_i)) g(p(e_i))$ with the $\sum_i dp(e_i)$ term going to zero if one considers that conservation of energy and particle number requires that $\sum dp(e_i) = 0$ and $\sum_i e_i dp(e_i) = 0$.

Reaction Balance

For the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) case, reaction balance is written as:

$$p(e_i) p(e_j) = p(e_k) p(e_l) \quad ((1a)), \text{ but only if } e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l \quad ((1b))$$

It is not enough to have one equation. ((1a)) shows that particle number is conserved, but that has nothing to do with the math form $p(e_i) p(e_j)$. This product represents something else. If one multiplies both sides of ((1a)) by $N_i N_j$, where N is the number of particles in an ideal gas, then:

$$N_i N_j = N_k N_l \quad ((2))$$

In other words, the total possible collisions of i and j particles (i.e particles with e_i and e_j) which is the product $N_i N_j$ in the MB case, must be the same as $N_k N_l$ due to time reversal balance because each possible reaction on the LHS must map to exactly one reaction on the RHS.

One may ask: How does reaction balance arise in the first place? We have argued in previous notes that it actually derives from considerations of a single Newtonian two body elastic interaction:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j \quad ((3))$$

Even in Newtonian mechanics one may not know the outcome of a collision, but if it is elastic energy must be conserved, and momentum is always conserved. Thus, the notion of probability is present at the single collision level.

$$((3)) \text{ may be generalized to: } e_k + e_l = e_i + e_j \quad ((4))$$

Then, every k,l pair must map to an e_i,e_j pair and extending this idea to an ideal gas with N_i particles with e_i yields the arguments given above. Thus, there is conservation beyond particle number and energy as stated above.

If one considers the Fermi-Dirac case, one may again focus on a single Newtonian reaction:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j \quad ((3))$$

Why is this not the same as the MB case? In a Fermi-Dirac (FD) collision, it is not just the two colliding particles which play a role, but the particles which are almost directly next to these colliding particles at the collision point. An e_1 cannot become an e_i if there is an e_i neighbour at the collision point, and a similar result holds for e_2 and e_j and e_k in the time reversal scenario. One may still extend this idea for a single elastic two body collision to an ideal gas, but one must write the total number of possible collisions in a different manner from the MB one.

In such a case, one must first pick out an e_1 particle. There are N_1 . Then, one must pick out a neighbour for e_1 and there are $N - N_1$ ways to do this so that the neighbour is not an e_i . For e_2 , there are N_2 , but there are $N - N_j$ possible neighbours. The total possible elastic successful collisions between e_1 and e_2 are:

$$N_1(1 - N_i) N_2 (1 - N_j) \quad ((5))$$

The products are e_i and e_j (such that ((3)) holds), but due to time reversal balance, one must have:

$$N_1(1 - N_i) N_2(1 - N_j) = N_i (1 - N_1) N_j (1 - N_2) \quad ((6))$$

$N_i = N p(e_i)$ and so one may combine ((6)) with $e_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j$ to solve for the FD distribution. Again there is energy conservation, particle number conservation (which is automatic in a two body collision with two particles on each side of an equation), but also a conservation of the number of possible collisions. Similar arguments hold for the Bose-Einstein case.

We note that the conservation of possible interactions occurs for an equilibrium value of $p(e_i)$. What happens if one shifts from equilibrium a little, i.e.

$$p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i) ? \quad ((7))$$

Shift From Equilibrium

The above arguments hold strictly for an equilibrium situation and yield the equilibrium $p(e_i)$. Due to energy and particle number conservation, one always has:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(e_i) = 1 \text{ and Sum over } i \text{ } e_i p(e_i) = E/N \quad ((8))$$

whether or not $p(e_i)$ represents the equilibrium probability. For example, if $p(e_i)$ shifts from the equilibrium value, then:

$$N_i = N p(e_i) \neq N C \exp(-e_i/T) \text{ in the MB case } ((9))$$

If one shifts from the equilibrium value of $p(e_i)$, then the reaction balance equations ((2)) and ((6)) (and a similar one for the BE case) no longer hold. One may, however, consider a slight shift such as ((7)). In such a case:

$$\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i e_i dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((10))$$

We have argued that reaction balance (which ensures a conservation of the number of possible collisions) cannot stand alone, independent of conservation of energy. In fact, a conservation of energy equation is required together with the reaction balance equation to solve for the equilibrium $p(e_i)$. One thus requires a function F which applied to both sides of a reaction balance equation converts a product into a sum. The \ln function is such a function. One must, however, also note that there are two constraints in ((10)) and not one. It is not enough to consider energy alone.

One should first consider for the FD case:

$$\ln(p(e_i) + dp(e_i)) + \ln(p(e_i) + dp(e_i)/p(e_i)) \quad \text{and} \quad \ln(1-p(e_i)-dp(e_i)) = \ln(1-p(e_i)) - dp(e_i) / (1-p(e_i)) \quad ((11))$$

If one wishes to have the $dp(e_i)$ terms sum to zero, one must consider what is necessary to make them represent combinations of ((10)). The identification of:

$$-e_i/T \text{ with } \ln(p(e_i)/(1-p(e_i))) \text{ follows from reaction balance } ((12))$$

Thus, the \ln pieces in ((11)) should be multiplied by $dp(e_i)$ to create $-e_i/T dp(e_i)$ which sums to zero, but the non- \ln terms need factors which remove the functions in the denominator. This leads to:

$$p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i) + (1-p(e_i)) \ln(1-p(e_i))) \text{ as the appropriate entropy function } ((13))$$

For the MB case, one drops the $1-p(e_i)$ term and for the BE case, one replaces $+$ with $-$ between the terms and changes $1-p(e_i)$ to $1+p(e_i)$. We have argued that reaction balance introduces a third conserved quantity, namely the number of possible reactions, and so we argue, as in previous notes that the quantity ((13)) has the appearance of a kind of conserved information, with two probabilities $p(e_i)$ and $1-p(e_i)$. One must consider changes in this conserved quantity with respect to changes in $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ and $\sum_i p(e_i)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that reaction-balance follows from a single two body elastic collision and is associated with three types of conservation: energy conservation, particle number conservation and the conservation of the total number of possible collisions. In the MB case, the total number of collisions of an e_i and e_j particle is $N_i N_j$ where $N_i = N p(e_i)$. Here $p(e_i)$ must be the equilibrium distribution. In the Fermi-Dirac case, one must worry about the immediate neighbour of e_i because an e_i cannot scatter into an e_k state if there is already an e_k as a neighbour. One must replace N_i in the MB case with $N_i (1 - N_k)$ etc. One may then write a balance of the number of total possible reactions. The equal sign appears due to time reversal balance, we argue. Thus: $N_i(1 - N_k) N_j(1 - N_l) = N_k(1 - N_i) N_l (1 - N_j)$. These conservation of the number of possible reactions must be considered together with conservation of energy if one is to solve for the equilibrium $p(e_i)$.

We next consider the case of fluctuations: $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$. Reaction balance only holds for the equilibrium $p(e_i)$ value and so one requires a different sort of analysis. We argue that $\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$ and $\sum_i e_i dp(e_i) = 0$ ((14)) due to particle number and energy conservation. We have argued that in the equilibrium case, there is a third conserved quantity (total number of possible interactions). Here we suggest that there should be a function of $p(e_i)$ which represents a conserved quantity such that $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$, together with the energy and particle number constraints ((14)) ensure that $\text{function}(p(e_i) + dp(e_i)) = \text{function}(p(e_i)) + \sum_i g(p(e_i) dp(e_i))$ such that the second term sums to 0. We then show that this leads to the entropy expressions, but consider it in terms of a conserved quantity which we call total (average) information, as in previous notes. Thus, a third conserved quantity appears at both the reaction balance level and the $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ level, we argue.